

Data Management Plan

fAlces project

“fAlces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures” – ERC Advanced Grant n.º 101140664

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Data Management Plan (DMP)

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fAlces – Facial Recognition Technologies. Etho-Assemblages and Alternative Futures
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About this document

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how the fAlces project will manage research data in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). It is based on the ERC Open Research DMP template, rewritten here for standalone public dissemination on Zenodo.

The project follows the principle: “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Metadata for all outputs will be openly available. Access to files will depend on ethical, legal, and contractual constraints, especially where biometric identifiers or risks of re-identification exist.

This DMP does not substitute for ethics compliance; it complements ethics approvals and GDPR compliance processes.

Planned public outputs and access approach (overview)

Public releases will be deposited in Zenodo as the analysis progresses. Sensitive/raw materials will not be made openly available. Where appropriate, Zenodo records may be metadata-only (with a public access statement) and/or files may be deposited under restricted visibility.

- **FAICES-DATASET-001-A:** Anonymised interview/focus group transcripts; interview guides; codebook; de-identification protocol. Public.
- **FAICES-DATASET-001-B:** De-identified fieldnote extracts and observation summaries; methodological appendices. Public or restricted (case-by-case).
- **FAICES-DATASET-001-C:** Web corpus (derived dataset): list of URLs + timestamps + annotations/features (not full copyrighted texts). Public.
- **FAICES-DATASET-001-D:** Co-produced media outputs (edited, consented versions) + production notes. Public (where agreed) or restricted.
- **FAICES-DATASET-001-R:** Raw audio/video or richly contextual materials that remain identifying or high risk. Not openly shared; access on request under data-use agreement.

Summary

The *fAICES* project explores the social, ethical, and political implications of facial recognition technologies through qualitative, multi-sited research. The study traces how FRTs are enacted, justified, contested, and reimagined across social worlds and settings by diverse social actors, including scientists, entrepreneurs, activists, Black communities, and artists.

The project curates an integrated research corpus (FAICES-DATASET-001) from interviews, focus groups, ethnographic observation (in-person and digital), document analysis, and collection of publicly available online materials.

Main data types and formats (working formats → preservation formats):

- Audio (recordings): .mp3/.wav → .wav (PCM) or .flac
- Transcripts and text: .docx/.txt → .txt and/or .odt
- Fieldnotes and logs: .docx/.txt → .txt and PDF/A
- Documents (annotated): .pdf/.docx → PDF/A
- Images: .jpg → .tiff or .png (where appropriate)
- Video: .mp4 → .mkv (where appropriate)
- Web-derived tables: .csv/.json (preservation-friendly as-is)

Estimated scale: approximately 100 interviews, 8–10 focus groups, extensive fieldnotes, and co-produced media outputs (subject to consent). Each public package will include a README, structured metadata, and a clear access/licensing statement.

1. Making data findable

Repository and persistent identifiers: Public releases will be deposited in Zenodo (Iscte community). Zenodo assigns DOIs and supports versioning, allowing the project to cite specific releases and a concept DOI for the evolving record. Internal working copies will remain on encrypted institutional servers.

Metadata: Each Zenodo record will include rich, machine-readable metadata (DataCite schema via Zenodo), including creators (with ORCID where available), affiliations, funding information (ERC grant number and acronym), keywords, dates, and related identifiers (links between the DMP, datasets, and publications).

Documentation: Every release will include a README describing the data, methods, file structure, de-identification steps, licence, access conditions, and version history. A simple catalogue of releases (CSV) will be maintained to make it easy to locate the latest public packages.

2. Making data openly accessible

The project follows the principle: “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.”

Open (public) releases will prioritise:

- Anonymised transcripts and curated extracts where re-identification risk is low.
- Non-sensitive observation summaries and methodological appendices.
- Templates and documentation (e.g., blank consent forms, interview guides, codebooks) where appropriate.
- Web-derived datasets limited to project-created data and metadata (e.g., URLs and annotations), respecting copyright and platform terms.

Sensitive materials will not be made openly available. This includes raw audio/video recordings, materials containing biometric identifiers, and any data whose disclosure could create risks for participants or communities. For such materials, the project will publish a public access statement (and, where appropriate, a restricted Zenodo record) explaining the conditions for access requests. Access, where granted, will be via a data-use agreement reviewed by the Principal Investigator and the institutional Data Protection Officer.

Safeguarding: For potentially vulnerable populations, additional measures (aggregation, redaction, paraphrasing, or restricted access) will be used to minimise re-identification risk. All releases are subject to ethics review, consent conditions, and GDPR-compliant processing.

3. Making data interoperable

Interoperability will be supported by:

- Use of preservation-friendly, widely supported formats (CSV, JSON, TXT, PDF/A; and suitable open audiovisual formats where appropriate).
- Metadata expressed in Zenodo/DataCite and exported where needed to Dublin Core, with social-science oriented documentation (DDI elements in codebooks where relevant).
- Controlled vocabularies for languages and places (e.g., ISO 639, standard geographic naming), and consistent naming conventions across releases.
- A project codebook (English) describing variables/codes and relationships to support reuse in common qualitative analysis tools.

4. Increasing data re-use

Timing and embargo: Anonymised/pseudonymised datasets will be released as soon as practicable and no later than one year after collection, unless ethical/legal considerations require an embargo or restricted access. Releases will be staged and versioned.

Licensing: For open releases, CC BY 4.0 is the default license (or CC 0 for non-sensitive web-scraped data). Where co-created media outputs require non-commercial restrictions, CC BY-NC

4.0 will be used with a clear rationale in the metadata. Metadata will be openly available and, where feasible, dedicated to the public domain (CC0) to support machine-actionable FAIRness.

Quality assurance: Transcripts undergo verification; automated and manual checks remove direct identifiers; and release packages include disclosure control notes. Audiovisual files, when shared, will be reviewed to ensure promised face/voice protections and participant approvals are respected.

Retention: Public releases in Zenodo will remain available long-term. Internal identifiable data will be retained only as long as necessary for the research and will be securely erased in line with institutional policy, ethics approvals, and participant withdrawal rights.

5. Allocation of resources and data security

Responsibilities: Day-to-day data management is led by the Principal Investigator and core team, supported by institutional IT services, the Ethics Committee, and the Data Protection Officer.

Costs: Zenodo does not charge deposit fees. Resource needs relate primarily to staff time for documentation, de-identification, metadata preparation, and curation.

Security: Working data are stored on encrypted institutional servers with role-based access control. Direct identifiers are separated from research materials at the earliest practical stage. Transfers between collaborators use end-to-end encrypted channels. Deletion events are logged and performed using secure erasure procedures.

International transfers: Where data cross borders outside the EEA, transfers will use appropriate safeguards (e.g., Standard Contractual Clauses under GDPR Article 46), and will be covered by explicit consent and, where relevant, local ethics clearance.

Controlled access model: For testimonies or experiential data from vulnerable participants, restricted access (or no open sharing) will be preferred even after de-identification, enabling reuse only under strict ethical conditions.

Disclaimer

This Data Management Plan does not substitute for ethics compliance. It remains the responsibility of the Principal Investigator to engage the ERC Ethics Team and institutional bodies regarding any concerns over data collection, processing, sharing, and storage.

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